

The Struggle of Poor People against the Capitalism in Australia in Carey's True History of the Kelly Gang

Ayu Rahma Ramadhan¹, Fathu Rahman², Herawaty Abbas³
^{1,2,3}Hasanuddin University
 Makassar, Indonesia

Abstract:- The aims of this research are to reveal the struggle of poor people against the capitalism in Australia which appear in the novel and to explain and reveal the consequences of being a rebel. This research used a qualitative descriptive method. The researcher used close reading to get the result of this research. The results of the research showed that there are many poor people that still struggling with poverty and discrimination and we cannot act arbitrarily because we have more privilege than some people. In this novel also show how Kelly's family struggle to live in peace. It also shows some consequences of being a rebel, like being in jailed, violence, and many more.

Keywords:- Peter Carey, Poverty, Struggles, Ned Kelly, Privileges.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human is a social creature. Even though humans are God's perfect creature, human still need interaction between others (Yohanah & MacLean, 2012). Humans also need another humans help for living. Humans usually do social interaction individually, individually with groups, or groups with groups (Lee, et al., 2005). Sometimes, there are some difference between humans that make individual or groups feels different with other and cause some social problem like, bullying, discrimination, and etcetera.

The novel True History of The Kelly Gang by Peter Carey is raised one of the social problems. The novel talks about poverty that caused discrimination to poor people specially Kelly's family and how poor people struggle to get their rights.

Poverty is one of serious social problem that happens in Indonesia and the World. There are many countries that still struggle to overcome poverty that end in discrimination to people that struggle in poverty (Sugiyartati, et al., 2020).

Literature represents and pictures out various aspects of life. According to Pradopo (1994:26) the literary work is as the picture of the world and human life, the main criteria that is putted on the literary work is truth, or everything that wants to be pictured by the author. Pradopo (1994:26-27) states that literature represents a language or a people: culture and tradition. But literature is more important than just a historical or cultural artifact (Nahdhiya, et al., 2022).

In addition, Wellek and Warren (1956: 3) state that the literature mirrors and expresses life that is even more ambiguous. It means that the literature is come up from the events happen in the society. In literature, the author presents

a work to delivers his or her ideas to the reader (Rahman, 2016).

Equally important, Jones (1986: 1) states that literature, it is broadening sense includes all written materials. Since the general grouping of materials will be in a vary various number; history books, philosophical works, novel, poems, plays, scientific articles, dictionaries, magazines, school textbooks, etcetera. Expresses the problem of life for which the author himself belongs. One of them is described in the novel.

II. RELATED THEORY

➤ *Sociology of Literature*

Literature is a product of sociology in term of the cultural. Sociology and literature have mutual relationship and related to one another (Rahman & Rahman, 2019). Sociology and literature both deal with social interaction and experience. According to Laeyendecker, (1983; 11-13) states that the emergence of sociology as science was triggered by the French revolution in 1789 to the 19th century. The impact was positive and negative on the surrounding community, but the negative impact at that time attracted the attention of theorists where chaos and disturbing disturbance arose in France due to the revolution. The community wants a new orderliness and social order, which triggers the attention of sociological theorist. People who think of social change and they are figures of sociology in the 20th century or better known as modern sociology figures, Sarton (1921), Karl Max (1818-1883), and Emile Durkheim (1858- 1917).

Comte (1798-1857) is known as the father of sociology because of his positive philosophical work, in his book Course de Philosophie Positive. In this book, there are three stages regarding the law of the progress of the human mind and society. That is theology as the first stage, metaphysics as the second stage, and positive as the last stage. The theology refers to all objects in the world having souls and that is a supernatural power. Metaphysics refers to humans still believing in abstract things and phenomena in this world containing powers that not owned by humans. According to Laeyendecker, (1983: 18-20) the positive is where human can explain and think scientifically about natural phenomena and social phenomena. All of the stages refer to the way human thinks, what's in human mind, and the society that the people living. Sociology is a social science that studies human societies, their interactions, and the processes that preserve and change them (Wheeler, 2006). It does this by examining the dynamics of constituent parts of societies such as institutions, communities, populations, and gender, racial, or age groups. Sociology also studies social status or

stratification, social movements, and social change, as well as societal disorder in the form of crime, deviance, and revolution (Nussbaum, 1992; Hasnia, et al., 2022).

Literature is creative and an art (Buell, et al., 2011). Some theorist argued that literature cannot be studied at all. We can only read, enjoy, and appreciate it. Literature is everything in print (Wellek, 2018). Furthermore, Greenlaw (1986) argued that 'nothing related to the history of civilization is beyond our province'; we are 'not limited to belles-lettres or even to printed or manuscript records in our effort to understand a period or civilization'. According to Nelson, et al., 1992) literary study has thus become not merely closely related to the history of civilization but indeed identical with it.

According to Pradopo (1994:26) the literary work is as the picture of human life, the main criteria that is putted on the literary work is 'truth', or everything that wants to be pictured by the author. Through that process, the reader of their literary work will be able to catch the characteristic of the author related with the world around them.

According to Morris (2005:81) states that literature introduce us to new world of experience means that the literary work is an immediate part of the literary environment, the aggregate of all the socially active literary works of a given epoch and social group. From a strictly historical point of view the individual literary work is a dependent and therefore actually inseparable element of the literary environment.

➤ *Australian literature*

Postcolonial issues in Australian Literature present thirteen new essays that address many of the numerous ways in which Australian literature is postcolonial and can be read using postcolonial reading strategies. The collection addresses a wide variety of Australian texts produced from the colonial period through the present, including works by, among others, Henry Lawson, Rolf Boldrewood, Miles Franklin, Xavier Herbert, Jack Lindsay, Patrick White, Francis Webb, James McAuley, Judith Wright, David Malouf, Elizabeth Jolley, Peter Carey, Richard Flanagan, Rodney Hall, Andrew McGahan, Kate Grenville, Tony Birch, Kim Scott, Alexis Wright, and Melissa Lucashenko (O'Reilly 2010:1).

The marginal status of Australian literature within the American academy more broadly and within postcolonial studies specifically is clearly evident in the American academic job market. (O'Reilly 2010:3) many works of Australian literature are postcolonial in terms of subject matter and technique, and Australian society is postcolonial in many ways (Khaerana, et al., 2022). However, many Australian texts do not engage with postcolonial issues at all, and Australian society can legitimately be viewed as other than postcolonial; for example, many indigenous Australian understand Australia as a colonial or neo-colonial society (O'Reilly 2010:6).

In Kim Scott essay "Covered Up with Sand" expresses doubt that contemporary Australia can be considered a postcolonial society due to a number of factors, including the tiny percentage of Australians who are descents of the indigenous peoples, Australia's failure to become an independent republic, the lack of power afforded to Indigenous peoples within Australian society, and the lack of a truly hybrid culture that blends Indigenous and colonial culture (Sukmawaty, et al., 2022).

Furthermore Nyaupane, (2019) also conducted a research with the object of the novel "True History of The Kelly Gang by Carey" entitled *Resistance to Colonial Ideology in the True History of Kelly Gang by Peter Carey*. This research explores Peter Carey's Post-Colonial Resistance by Rewriting the Life and History of Iconic Australian Bandit Ned Kelly in the True History of the Fictional Kelly Gang. In the novel, Carey has presented details of Kelly's life and events. Moreover, in contrast to the official colonial historical narrative, Carey is able to portray his positive character as more than just a bandit by reviewing history from the perspective of historically marginalized people strong postcolonial sense resistance. In addition, Carey as a post-colonial writer has captured the sentiments of ordinary Australians and wrote about the life and history of colonizer Ned Kelly. In this regard, he has fought colonial notions of Ned Kelly and made him a national hero, icon or legend against the social and political structures that oppressed the colonialists. Peter Carey has resurrected this historical figure as a true Australian legend as if he were fighting culture, history and colonial domination. In this sense, the novel stands as an official historical counter or as a means of postcolonial resistance. Through True History of the Kelly Gang, Carey defies colonial officials' views by rewriting myths such as Ned Kelly's life in novel form. By doing so, it became clear that he had a strong sense of postcolonial resistance (Carey, 2007; Sukmawaty, et al., 2022).

In addition, Zaenurrosyid (2016) conducted a research entitled *The Struggle for Law Enforcement and the Politics of Capitalism in the Indonesian Context*. Law, economics has one vision, happiness for all. The author finds that there is inequality in Indonesia's economic growth, this is an important issue for socio-economic productivity. In this research, Marxist theory of class and conflict is applied to analyze it in the Indonesian context. Neoliberalism has become a capitalist ideology as legitimacy supported by international institutions, such as the World Bank, IMF, etc. The rule of law in terms of dynamic regulation in Indonesia is part of an alternative solution to controlling socio-economic equality supported by progressive law in the contemporary era.

Moreover, Bahtiyar, (2015) also conducted a research entitled *Criticism of Islam Against the Concept of Marxism Regarding Poverty Alleviation*. As a social reality, poverty cannot be eliminated absolutely, but it can be overcome and repaired so that it does not destroy humanity. Poverty as a reality of life is always described as a condition of life that is lacking, weak and powerless to meet the needs of life, both in

a spiritual and material sense. The purpose of this study is to find out the concept of poverty alleviation according to Marxism, and also to criticize the concept from the point of view of Islam as a religion. This research is a type of library research; namely the data and study materials that are used are derived from library sources, whether in the form of books, encyclopedias, journals, magazines, newspapers, papers and others. The form of this research is descriptive-comparative-analytical.

Moreover, Saragih, (2018) discussed about film entitled *Hyperreality and the Power of Capitalism in Film in Time*. This paper aims to show the forms of hyper reality and the power of capitalism that occur in the film *In Time* (2011), a dystopian American science fiction film that depicts the illusion of life that occurs in the 22nd century. The film depicts a society in which people genetically stop aging at the age of 25. Their age will then be determined on the time holdings shown on their "time watch". This film compares the lives of two different societies, Dayton – a poor society – and New Greenwich – a rich society. This study uses Jean Baudrillard's theory of signs, simulations, hyper reality, and consumption society. The result of this study is the discovery of the characteristics of hyper reality in the film *In Time* which is shown consistently through the depiction of people's lives in the city of New Greenwich. This hyper reality is reflected in the existence of immortality, youth, and extravagance or consumerism in New Greenwich's bourgeois society. Mastering becomes very influential on the creation of the hyper reality world. The power of capitalism has succeeded in forming a consumer society trapped in a black hole of needs, both worthy and symbolic.

The last researcher is Prentis, (2013) entitled *Fictional Man: Ned Kelly in Peter Carey's True History of the Kelly Gang in Comparison with Older Portrayals*. This thesis discusses the analysis of various aspects of the personality of the protagonist of Peter Carey – Ned Kelly's *True History of the Kelly Gang* (2000). Although a historical figure, Ned Kelly is approached as a fictional character with focus placed on his symbolic status on Australian nationality, myth and maturity, and on the literary means of demonstrating. A separate aspect is placed in the evolution of context by comparison with older depictions of the same character – in Max Brown and J.J. Kenneally's *The Complete Inner History of the Kelly Gang and Their Pursuits* (1929), all of which take a heroic approach to men. The work shows that Ned Kelly can be perceived in many complex ways, with the possibility of further analysis being suggested. Comparing the three books, it was found that although there were considerable unifying tendencies and moments, some aspects had significant differences in focus or emphasis. The shift is noted from the confrontational defense of idealization of the so-called historical people to the more mystical glorification of imperfection. No other clear development trend was found, although a more extensive comparison with further books on the subject may provide a better picture.

III. METHODS

In collecting the data, the researcher used library research method and close reading to get information about this research. In this research, the researcher used *True History of the Kelly Gang* by Peter Carey as the primary data. The author also reads some books, and journal articles to support this research as the additional data. This is very important to support the information that the author needs. Then the author analyzed the data.

IV. FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The Struggle and The Discrimination of the poor people was found and there are some discrimination that poor people get in the novel *True History of The Kelly Gang*. First is when Kelly's mom try to send a prisoner named Quinn a cake because Kelly's father were absent and cannot took the cake by themselves to the prison. A man from prison said that the cake cannot go to the prisoner without him and said that he will check the cake first. But instead checking the cake, he broke the cake in front of Ned Kelly and his mom.

Tis not poverty I hate the most
Nor the eternal frovelling
But the insult which grow on it
Which not even leeches can cure (Carey, 2000: 9)

In this quote shows that the prison guard did discrimination to Kelly's family by broke the cake that Kelly's mom took to the prison, and it makes Kelly feel the insult from the higher-income people that he met that day.

For the great offence of duffing a bullock with cancer of the eye he were interred in this earth floored slab hut which could not have measured more than 6ft x 6ft and here my mother were forced to kneel in the mud and push the broken cake under the door. (Carey 2000: 6)

In this quote doing of the prison guard is crystal clear that he did Ned Kelly's family dirty by forcing Ned's mom kneeled in the mud and pushing the broken cake through the door gap.

In this quote below, it shows how a man trying to leading Ned's family into depth by offering a land to be labored.

The Duffy Land Act of 1862 it gave a man or widow the right to select a block between 50 and 640 acres for £1 per acre part payable on selection the rest over 8 year. My mother were for it but my father were againts it, he said the graet Charkes Gavan Duffy was a well-intentioned idiot leading poor men into debt and lifelong labour (Carey 2000: 22)

The next data is after Ned's father was imprisoned because of Ned. This moment shows their struggle to move on with life.

Our lives were far harder for his absence. The landlord provides no decent fences so the mother and her children was obliged to build a dogleg fence 2 mi. Long to save our cows from impounding. In any case our stock would still escape the fines was 5/- for cow 3/- for a pig, this we could ill afford. (Carey 2000: 28)

The next is the situation when the first winter happens, and they face struggle to their living.

That 1st winter we had parsnips and potatoes only. We had to sell the wagon and 2 horses but kept our small herd of dairy cows. We produced 2 lb. of butter per day but rarely had anything except lard for our own bread. (Carey 2000: 29)

In this context, the situation shows how Irish people were ripped from their homeland, Ireland.

When our brave parents was ripped from Ireland like a teeth from the mouth of their own history and every dear familiar thing had been abandoned on the docks of Cork or Galway or Dublin then the Banshee come on board the cursed convict ships the ROLLA and the TELICHERRY and the RODNEY and the PHEOBE DUNBAR (Carey 2000: 108)

The next quotation, it shows that how a Chinaman try to degrade Ned Kelly by telling him to pick up marbles from the ground by force

Boy got plenty time, he said then pushed the marbles at me so I knocked his hand away and the marbles spilled onto the ground like quondong seeds.
Pickee up, said he
You going to be ordered by a Chinaman, Annie asked me.
I aint said I and sat back down to take the plate of boiled eggs as Annie passed them (Carey, 2000: 118)

➤ *The Consequences of Being a Rebel in the Novel*

The researcher finds in this novel some consequences of being a rebel, it is happening because of many factors, for example to please their family of helping others. First quotation is when Ned Kelly kill one of Murray beast to feed their family

I killed my little heifer badly and am sorry for it still. By the time she fell her neck was a sea of laceration I will never forget the terror in her eyes. And this is how my ma found me with

the poor dead creature at my feet
and my hair and shirt soaked with
blood and gore. (Carey 2000: 25)

Not too long after that situation, when Ned's father find and cut out the brand of the beast so no one will accuse them for stealing, there is a police come to their house 2 days later. The police find out that the Kelly's family has killed Murray's beast by finding heifer's hide that they hide before

I entered the hut and my father were sitting in his usual chair watching a lanky fair haired constable spreading out the heifer's hide across our table.

Come on John, said Constable Doxcy putting his hand right through the hole where the brand had been. John we know what missing here (Carey 2000: 26)

After verifying some data, it turned out that the cowhide was the missing Murray Cow and the police took Ned Kelly's father to prison, even though it was Ned Kelly who killed the cow.

Thus were father taken from me
handcuffed to the stirrup iron of
Doxcy's mare (Carey 2000: 28)

V. CONCLUSION

The study concludes that the study shows that there are still many poor people who are still struggling with poverty and discrimination and we cannot act arbitrarily because it has more rights than a few people. This novel also shows how the Kelly family struggles to live in peace. Furthermore, it also shows some of the consequences of being a rebel, such as imprisonment, violence, and more.

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